

A rebuttal of the derivation of the Nernst theorem from the vanishing of the heat capacity at zero temperature

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Yan *et al.* [1] derived the Nernst's theorem (or postulate) from the vanishing heat capacity at zero temperature. Yet the inference was not correct.

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The Nernst theorem is one of the general properties of matter in the close vicinity to the zeroth isotherm. It was derived from the observation of chemical equilibrium properties and from the vanishing of thermal expansion coefficient at low temperature.[2] The theorem states that “the isothermal change of entropy $(\Delta S)_t$ vanishes as the temperature vanishes”.

Formally the theorem sets the vanishing of the coefficient $(\partial S/\partial y)_t = (\partial x/\partial T)_y = (\partial^2 A/\partial T \partial y)$, where x, y are suitable mechanical parameters such as the pressure/volume or the magnetic field/magnetization, and A is a suitable thermodynamic potential like the free energy or the free enthalpy. Stability does not restrict the domain of this coefficient.

One of the main consequences of the Nernst theorem is the fact that $\lim_{T \rightarrow 0} S(T, y)$ is unique if it exists.

The vanishing of the specific heats close to the zeroth isotherm is another kind of evidence in itself.[3] It refers to the fact that the susceptibility $C_x/T = (\partial S/\partial T)_y = -(\partial^2 A/\partial T^2)$ has a ceil —ie does not become exceedingly large— as the temperature vanishes. As a consequence the limit $\lim_{T \rightarrow 0} S(T, y)$ does exist.

The Nernst theorem and the vanishing of the specific heat makes $S(0, y)$ a unique, finite number that can be set to zero.[4] Since $(\partial S/\partial T)$ must be positive by stability, it is deduced that $S(T, y) > S(0, y), \forall T > 0$ and $\forall y$. Hence, no adiabatic change in y can bring the system to the zeroth isotherm, which is the unattainability statement.

The relationship between the Nernst theorem, the unattainability statement and the vanishing of the specific heats has raised some confusion and clarification earlier[5–9] and later.[10, 11]

Yan *et al.* attempted to derive the vanishing of $(\Delta S)_t$ from the vanishing of C_y . They considered a reversible adiabatic process that cools the sample by varying the mechanical parameter y from y_1 to y_2 . With $(\Delta y)_s = y_2 - y_1$ they arrived to:

$$(\Delta S)_t = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial y} \right)_t (\Delta y)_s = -C_y \frac{(\Delta T)_s}{T}, \quad (1)$$

where $(\Delta T)_s$ is the adiabatic change of temperature when y goes from y_2 to y_1 .

They then argued that since $-(\Delta T)_s < T$ —the system can not reach temperatures below $T = 0$ — the vanishing of C_y leads to the vanishing of the RHS of Equation (1). Hence, the vanishing of $(\Delta S)_t$ is derived without further assumptions.

However, if the Nernst theorem is not granted and the vanishing of the specific heats is granted, then $S(T, y)$ is not unique at the zeroth isotherm. It is a spectrum $S(T, 0) \in [S_l, S_h] \subset \mathbb{R}$. Figure 1 shows this scenario. Consider the equilibrium state E_1 reached isothermally after setting y_1 so that its entropy S_1 fulfills $S_1 \in [S_l, S_h]$. Then, varying y adiabatically from y_1 to y_2 , the sample is cooled, can reach $T = 0$, and it would only reach y_2 at some temperature $T < 0$ (E_2). Equation (1) refers the thermophysical properties of substance and conceptually links the properties of E_1 to the properties of E_2 . Therefore, in Equation (1) $-(\Delta T)_s$ must be larger than T , contrary to Yan *et al.*'s assumptions. Irrespective of this, the adiabatic cooling would arrive at $T = 0$ when the mechanical parameter reaches y_3 , determined by the equation $S_1 = S(0, y_3)$ (see E_0 in the Figure).

The example in Figure 1 is purely educational. No such physical system has ever been observed. The thing to note here is that the derivation by Yan *et al.* assumed, implicitly, that such behaviour was not possible. Inadvertently they were deriving the Nernst theorem assuming

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Figure 1. A simple rebuttal of the derivation made by Yan *et al.*. The specific heat vanishes at $T = 0$ (noted by the finite values of the entropy). If the Nernst theorem is not granted then the entropy is a spectrum at $T = 0$. Then an adiabatic process $y_1 \rightarrow y_2$ can reach the zeroth isotherm at y_3 . Equation (1) links the properties of E_1 to the properties of E_2 . Contrary to Yan *et al.*'s assumptions $-(\Delta T)_s$ can be larger than T_1 . The example is purely educational: no physical system shows this behaviour.

one of the consequences of the Nernst theorem, which is the unattainability of the zeroth isotherm.

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